

Investigation of corrosion fatigue behavior of stainless steels 304L and 316L in MEA-based solutions

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1. Introduction

Amine absorption with monoethanolamine (MEA) is the benchmark technology for post-combustion CO₂ capture [1,2], but the corrosive environment in capture units promotes corrosion fatigue [3]. Stainless steels 304L and 316L are commonly used, though their durability in MEA solutions containing SO_x and NO_x impurities is not fully established. This study evaluates their corrosion and corrosion fatigue behavior under CO₂-loaded and unloaded conditions to clarify degradation mechanisms and support material selection for more reliable capture systems.

2. Experimental / Methodology

In this study, the corrosion and corrosion fatigue behavior of 304L and 316L stainless steels was examined in monoethanolamine (MEA) solutions at 25°C. For the electrochemical experiments, a three-electrode cell was used to provide the polarization curves. For the fatigue experiments, a custom setup with a vertically moving piston applied cyclic bending to C-ring specimens immersed in the corrosive medium. Tests were conducted under constant amplitude loading with a stress ratio $R = \sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max} = 0$ and a frequency of 20 Hz, and the results were used to construct S-N curves for both alloys. Comparative tests in corrosion-free environments were also carried out. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provided insight into the failure mechanisms and the role of corrosion in fatigue crack initiation and propagation.

3. Results and Discussion

Results revealed that the introduction of CO₂, HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ reduced the corrosion resistance of both stainless steels, due to the action of oxidizing agents. Also, it was observed that all corrosive solutions significantly contributed to the reduction of fatigue life in both stainless steels. Notably, the MEA loaded solution containing SO_x/NO_x pollutants, which exhibited the higher corrosion rate, resulted in the lowest corrosion fatigue life. Additionally, SS 316L demonstrated superior fatigue life compared to SS 304L, while SS 304L showed multiple crack initiation sites. SEM analysis indicated that the fracture surfaces remained similar, regardless of the amine solution used, with the fracture type changing along the crack propagation direction.

Figure 1. S-N curves for 304L and 316L stainless steels immersed in various MEA-based solutions, at the temperature of 25°C.

4. Conclusions

The corrosion resistance of both steels was found to vary depending on the specific amine solution. Among the tested environments, the MEA solution loaded with SO_x/NO_x was the most aggressive, leading to the lowest fatigue life. Nevertheless, the features of the fracture surfaces indicated that the failure mechanism remained essentially independent of the particular corrosive solution employed.

5. References

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